

Equivalent Units of Production in Unit Cost Calculation for Fair Pricing of Pharmaceuticals: A Scoping Review

Working paper

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Abstract

Objective: This scoping review aimed at mapping evidence on equivalent units of production related to unit cost calculation formula for fair pricing of pharmaceuticals.

Introduction: As the global pharmaceuticals' prices persistently rise, so is containment calls from society if universal health coverage goals are to be realised. Regardless of pricing method unit cost is still the foundation for determining prices, yet its management accounting convention- based formula associated with fair pricing is insufficiently researched.

Inclusion criteria: Sources that reported on equivalent units of production, unit cost of production in the manufacturing industry, value-based pricing, and fair pricing of pharmaceuticals/ or drugs/or medicines, were included.

Methods: We searched for published and unpublished studies written in English without time limit to 2022 in Google Scholar, Scopus, Science Direct, Web of Science and gray literature in selected websites and digital repositories. Finally, we used JBI scoping review methodology.

Results: A total of 27/243 sources were included in the review, comprising 8 papers each on equivalent units of production and production costs; 1 on manufacturing costs in financial statements while last 10 were on pricing; 3 being on fair pricing. Definition of fair pricing for pharmaceuticals is still inadequate in management accounting context. Moreover, there was no study on calculation of unit cost of pharmaceuticals in accordance with continuous process costing convention.

Conclusions: Unit cost of production based on management accounting convention is critical for an acceptable definition of fair pricing for pharmaceuticals. There is a need for more research on unit costs of pharmaceuticals in order to facilitate a synthesis of the literature.

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KEYWORDS: equivalent units of production, unit costs of pharmaceuticals, fair pricing of pharmaceuticals, scoping review

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